

THE PRACTICING OF TV NEWS, MOVIES, CARTOON AND TED TALKS VIDEO RESOURCES AS SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS IN THE TEACHING ENGLISH INTEGRATED SKILLS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: The Videos, movies, TV news, cartoon and Ted talks are good educational tools. When used intelligently and moderately, they may enhance the educational approach and make it more real, dynamic, vivid, and participative. participants' motions and develop skills like empathy. Educate kids about several languages and support their academic work. The use of movies promotes the brain processes of reasoning, problem-solving, decision-making, and creativity. Videos go beyond tasks that call on recall and connection from the student. Use videos to engage viewers with more challenging topics and to promote ongoing engagement with the information. Movies are a useful resource for individuals who learn visually since they allow for the perception of subjects without the learning barriers.

Keywords: TV news, movies, cartoon, Ted talks, listening, speaking, reading, writing, film, teaching and learners.

Introduction. TV, video, and movies are effective teaching resources. They may make the teaching method more real, dynamic, vivid, and participatory when utilized wisely and moderately. movements of the participants and hone abilities like empathy. Introduce students to various languages and aid in their study. The utilization of movies encourages the mental functions of thinking, reasoning, solving problems, making decisions, and creating. Videos go beyond exercises that require the learner to recollect and connect. Use videos to draw viewers in with more complicated subjects and to encourage continued interaction with the material. The ability to perceive topics without the obstacles to learning makes movies a valuable resource for those who learn visually. Like novels, movies provide pupils a glance of many individuals and how they perceive the world and deal with various situations.

TV news

Wodak said that during the past 20 years, the production of television news has significantly increased in both English-speaking and non-English-speaking nations. Availability of Efl TV news is actually widespread. English-language TV news broadcasting is a substantial and growing source of non- reciprocal listening opportunities as well as an immediate and significant alternative information source. Thus, the instructional and informative components of English newscasts may frequently and significantly overlap. When assessing the academic value of TV news, there are three main categories to consider:

- formal strategies, or audience knowledge of the genre and institution building of TV news as whole in particular cultural settings;
- the language confidence and gain with incorporating visual and aural information;
- the background knowledge or content schemata watchers need to fully comprehend a news piece;

Both native speakers as well as non-native speakers may discover that qualities like curiosity, determination, and knowledge are more important than language proficiency when it comes to understanding TV news.

Weissenreider examined the effects of both textual and content schemata in an assessment of intermediate and advanced students' listening comprehension of television. Weissenreider claims that the interplay of textual in addition to content schemata and effective listening strategies leads to their understanding. Before discussing the newscast's real substance, the topic must be aware of its textual structure, including the anchor's introduction, the writer's introduction, the correspondent narrating the narrative over action video, an interview, etc.

Meinhof argues that rather than the grammatical difficulty of the texts, second language learners' difficulties absorbing TV news are caused by a lack of grasp of the preparation services of the medium. Because News channel is a highly organized genre, students can develop "metadiscursive" skills that let them anticipate ideas, focus on crucial details of a news story, and ignore less significant ones. Meinhof goes on to describe the "great frequency concept" of television news, which she refers to as its core elements.

Newscasts should be used for listening exercises, according to Brinton and Gaskil, who also mentioned how these lessons work. Teachers showed more enthusiasm and motivation for the subject matter, despite preparation (the instructor will have to type up the tv networks beforehand) and the possibility that pupils would have felt powerless due to the frequency of local speaking.

Bell distinguishes between news stories with endogenous information and those that have exogenous information, emphasizing that the latter can be understood without specialized knowledge while the former requires prior knowledge. Although different degrees of prior knowledge are likely necessary for different news items in order to be understood, this variation is nevertheless beneficial because more complicated stories may require more scaffolding and prelistening exercises. It may be wiser to stay away from exogenous situations that need a great deal of specialized expertise. Other considerations are the loudness of the visual accompaniment and any language barriers.

Movies

Geddes & Sturtridge asserted that media have a significant part in the process of producing literary content. If the instructor selected the right media, the lesson might be presented to the pupils successfully. One form of media to generate writing material is the movie. A movie is a collection of moving images and sound that conveys a narrative. An optional technique for encouraging pupils' critical thinking is a movie. It aids in the integration of audio with motion video before being written into a story movie by pupils.

Khan discussed "Utilizing Movies in the ESL Classroom to Improve Non-Native Students' Language Skills" in his speech. She claimed that increasing access to audiobooks, such as movies, can significantly boost second language acquisition for non-native English language learning contexts. She made the case that movies give English teachers a creative opportunity to aid them in more effective teaching. In order for it to thrive in the future, support for education is a must. Schools can

take a more proactive approach to promoting the use of films in ESL teaching by being more adaptable, encouraging, and proactive.

Authors J. Flowerdew and L. Miller When teaching FMs in EFL lessons, hearing is the most crucial integrated skill, regardless of whether the chosen movies are being shown with or without subtitles. At the movies, it's possible to observe people who have the ability to listen for long periods of time, usually to longer speeches. Depending just on students' level of English proficiency, the movies might also be screened without subtitles, which would benefit the students' training in listening skills.

Cartoon

As according Khoshniyat and Dowlatabadi, Disney movies are utilized to teach English listening and expressing to young learners. Disney movies are used to learn better English easier and to create an enjoyable and interesting learning environment. The illustrative movies enable students to communicate and listen with a great deal more effectiveness. They said that using movies to teach English can combine the context of language learning with creativity, making language lessons more motivating and enjoyable.

According to Thakur, cartoons are drawings that highlight a certain physical trait, mannerism, or attribute of the subject. Cartoons could be used as teaching tool to improve students' linguistic skills and to transmit human emotions, values, and morals in an effort to alter the public's perceptions. So why not use cartoons in our schools to communicate important ideas via the power of their pictures and words.

Bahrani & Soltani assert that the visual effect of cartoons, captions, and word hints affects learners to react better regardless of their age, background, or competence level. The comedy, sarcasm, and ethical or moral message weaved within cartoons persuade the pupils to appreciate the duties associated to cartoons.

According to Van Wyk, the lessons on cartoons are extremely participatory and provide pupils a chance to debate and express their opinions with other students. The high response rate from the pupils eventually leads to the development of their own interpretation of learning and higher-order cognitive abilities.

Ted talks

Any teacher may use TED talks in the classroom to assist students develop a number of abilities, including value awareness, general cultural, analytical, and conversational skills, in addition to personal self-improvement skills, in light of the fact that they are a highly-liked form of entertainment.

According to Coffin, the educational approach makes use of TED Talks materials, which professors may use to educate speaking classes at secondary and tertiary universities. The lexical material of TED Talks lectures is fairly vast and comprises a broad range of terminology, idiomatic, phraseological units, and fundamental everyday phrases that may be useful while learning English. Before choosing a film, teachers must ensure that its lexical structure corresponds to the pupils' level of language competency. By indicating the likely degree of student difficulty, the lexical structure for TED Talks presentation should help the English teacher prepare lessons. For academic objectives, TED Talks might well be utilized to develop English courses.

According to Medal, TED has started to expand after twenty years and also is expanding in a constructive way. TED sponsors several events and programs, such as TEDx, TED Fellow, and

others. Without a question, TED is the center of the ideas that are changing the world. First of all, TED Talks are incredibly inspiring. The variety of accessible motivating films will enthrall the educators, who could even pick up valuable lessons from watching videos alone. On www.ted.com, a number of talks are available. Currently, you may download and stream these speeches online. As TED has grown, the subjects addressed in TED Talks have expanded and have even begun to touch on areas like economics, health, and education.

Conclusion

TV, video, and movies can make the teaching method more real, dynamic, vivid, and participatory when utilized wisely. Movies provide pupils a glance of many individuals and how they perceive the world and deal with various situations. Videos go beyond exercises that require the learner to recollect and connect.

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